

Polyolefin separators for rechargeable lithium-ion batteries

Amir Mohsen Fani Saberi, Mohammad Fasihi*

*School of Chemical Engineering, Iran University of Science and Technology, Tehran
16846-13114, Iran*

**Corresponding author: mfasihi@iust.ac.ir*

Abstract

In this paper, the types and characteristics of polyolefin separators for lithium-ion batteries are reviewed. In recent years, there have been some efforts to develop advanced battery separators for rechargeable lithium-ion batteries for different applications. The separator is an important component of lithium-ion batteries. It provides a barrier between the positive and negative electrodes to prevent electrical short circuits. Also it serves as the electrolyte reservoir for the transport of ions during the charging and discharging cycles of a battery. This paper introduces the requirements of battery separators and the structure and properties of polyolefin separators.

Keywords: Separator; Lithium-ion; Batteries; Polyolefin

1- Introduction

Nowadays, lithium-ion batteries have received extensive attention as the most suitable energy storage system for many portable electronic devices. They are also one of the most promising candidates as the large-scale power source for electric vehicles because they have several important advantages including long cycle life and low self-discharging. Similar to the Galvanic cells, a lithium-ion battery consists of three functional components, i.e., the anode (negative electrode), cathode (positive electrode), and electrolyte (Fig. 1). When the battery is discharged, lithium ions move from the anode to the cathode through the non-aqueous electrolyte, carrying the current. During charging, an external electrical power source forces the current to pass in the reverse

direction and make lithium ions migrate from the cathode to the anode across the electrolyte [1,2].

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of a typical lithium-ion battery

The separator is placed between the anode and the cathode. In a lithium-ion battery, the essential function of the separator is to prevent the physical contact of electrodes while serving as the electrolyte reservoir to enable ionic transport. So, it should be non-conductive, but porous. The preparation and properties of polyolefin type are discussed in this paper.

2- Polyolefin separator process

Polyolefin separator can be prepared by two different manufacturing methods: the wet process and dry process. In both methods polymer thin films prepare first. The diagram of these two process is shown in Fig. 2. The dry process generally consists of heating, extruding, annealing, and stretching steps. The annealing step is applied to improve the crystalline structure of the polymer. The annealed film is then stretched along the machine direction to form micropores. The dry process is technologically convenient since no solvents are used during the process. Celgard and Ube Industries provide PP and PE microporous separators by the dry process.

The wet process is based on the solvent extraction. This process includes four steps as shown in Fig. 2b. The first step is the mixing and heating of the polymer, hydrocarbon oil, and other additives to form a homogenous solution. The second step is to extrude the thin film. The third step is to extract the oil and other additives with a volatile solvent to form the microporous structure. The fourth step, the stretching of the film, can be conducted before or after the extraction of oil and additives to achieve desirable porosity and pore size [3].

Fig 2. Fabrication processes of polyolefin separator: (a) dry and (b) wet processes

3- The morphology of different separators

Separators made by dry process have slit-like pores, while those from the wet process show interconnected and elliptical pores. The membranes formed by the dry process are more appropriate for high power density batteries because of their open and straight porous structure. On the other hand, the separator prepared by the wet process are more suitable for long cycle life. Fig. 3 shows the SEM images of separators made by different company [4].

4- Conclusions

The separator is an important component in rechargeable lithium-ion batteries. The main role of the separator is to prevent physical contact between the positive and negative electrodes of the battery and to prevent internal short while serving as the electrolyte reservoir to enable ionic transport. Currently, microporous polyolefin separators are the most commonly used separator for rechargeable lithium-ion batteries.

These are produced by two methods and each one has some advantage. However, polyolefin separators can still be improved in terms of conductivity, thermal stability, and wettability for the higher performance batteries.

Figure 3. SEMs of (a) Celgard separator using dry process; (b) Asahi using wet process; (c) Entek using wet process; (d) Tonen using wet process

References

- [1] A. Pankaj et al. Chemical reviews 104, 4419-4462 ,(2004).
- [2] Sh. Santhanagopalan, Batteries for Sustainability. Springer New York, (2013).
- [3] V. Deimede, et al. Energy Technology 3, 453468, (2015).
- [4] M. Yang, et al. Membranes, 2, 367-383, (2012).